

ADAPTATION OF YOUNG PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS.

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Abstract. *The relevance of research on the adaptation of young physical education teachers is dictated by the modern challenges of Russian education, primarily the need to meet the targets of the national project "Education", in particular, "70% of teachers under the age of 35 will be involved in various forms of support and support in the first three years of work, by the end of 2024." Young teachers, including physical education teachers, in the conditions of the new geopolitical reality are the strategic resource that should become the main one in the formation of a new paradigm of education in Uzbekistan.*

The aim of the study is to assess the adaptation process of young physical education teachers in Yekaterinburg, to identify the main reasons for the difficulty of entering the profession and moving to the next stage of professional development. The article was written on the basis of the study conducted by the authors in May 2023. research of young teachers – teachers of physical culture, whose experience does not exceed five years.

In total, 20 teachers of Yekaterinburg schools were interviewed. Socio-professional adaptation is understood as "the process of interaction between the individual and the professional environment, during which the development of goals, values, norms of professional activity is carried out, due to a combination of external and internal factors that ensure the optimal functioning and development of the individual in the profession."

Keywords: *adaptation, young teachers of physical culture, professional adaptation, socio-psychological adaptation.*

АДАПТАЦИЯ МОЛОДЫХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ ВОСПИТАНИЯ.

Аннотация. *Актуальность исследований по вопросам адаптации молодых учителей физической культуры продиктована современными вызовами российского образования, в первую очередь необходимостью достижения целевых показателей национального проекта «Образование», в частности «70% учителей в возрасте до 35 лет». будет задействован в различных формах поддержки и поддержки в первые три года работы, до конца 2024 года».*

Молодые учителя, в том числе учителя физкультуры, в условиях новой геополитической реальности являются тем стратегическим ресурсом, который должен стать основным в формировании новой парадигмы образования в Узбекистане. Цель исследования - оценить процесс адаптации молодых учителей физкультуры Екатеринбурга, выявить основные причины трудностей вхождения в профессию и перехода на следующий этап профессионального развития. Статья написана на основе проведенного авторами в мае 2023 г. исследования молодых педагогов – учителей физической культуры, стаж которых не превышает пяти лет. Всего было опрошено 20 учителей екатеринбургских школ.

Под социально-профессиональной адаптацией понимают «процесс взаимодействия личности и профессиональной среды, в ходе которого осуществляется развитие целей, ценностей, норм профессиональной деятельности, за счет сочетания внешних и внутренних факторов, обеспечивающих оптимальное функционирование и развитие личности в профессии».

Ключевые слова: адаптация, молодые учителя физической культуры, профессиональная адаптация, социально-психологическая адаптация.

The problems of adaptation of young specialists invariably attract the attention of researchers, in particular, the formation of the teacher's personality in the process of professional adaptation is deeply studied in the works of others. A valuable contribution to the study of adaptation processes has become the work of any novice teacher, like any young specialist, is faced with standard types of adaptation: "professional adaptation is the improvement of professional abilities based on additional development of knowledge and skills, the formation of professionally necessary personal qualities, a positive attitude to their work.

Psychophysiological adaptation is the mastering of the totality of all conditions that have a different psychophysiological effect on an employee during work. Socio-psychological adaptation is the adaptation of an employee to the manager, the team and the organization, his inclusion in the system of relationships between the members of the team with its traditions, norms of life, value orientations." Next, we consider adaptation "as a multicomponent dynamic education consisting of three components: communicative, emotional, motivational." Nevertheless, in the process of adaptation of young physical education teachers, of course, there are their own peculiarities.

Because, according to the opinion, "the professional activity of a physical education teacher is a complex activity in its psychological content, requiring from a specialist not only knowledge of the theory and practice of teaching and upbringing, but also the ability to organize the process of physical education of schoolchildren, which is based, among other things, on the personal qualities of the teacher, his motivational and value attitude to professional activity".

Thus, it can be stated that in the process of adaptation to the profession for a young teacher of physical culture, in addition to the actual professional knowledge and skills, the formation of his subjective and personal sphere plays a special role, since in the process of education he is responsible not only for the psychological well-being of his students, but also for his physical, bodily health, which imposes additional responsibility on the teacher and involves him in additional professional risks. To identify difficulties in the adaptation of young physical education teachers in Yekaterinburg, the authors conducted a study in which 20 teachers under 35 years of age, whose work experience does not exceed 5 years, took part (Figure 1).

12 Physical education teachers: 5 men (all have higher secondary education) and 7 women (5 people have higher education and 2 respondents have secondary vocational education) (Fig. 2.)

The main criteria for the adaptation of young physical education teachers were:

- 1) identification of readiness for professional activity;
- 2) determining the degree of job satisfaction in an educational organization;
- 3) determination of the degree of emotional comfort.

1. All respondents note life satisfaction over the past year, only 50% are satisfied with their professional activities, while 90% of respondents understand their professional duties well and the same number noted that they are satisfied with the status of a teacher in an educational institution. This indicates a high motivation for professional activity among young professionals with reduced satisfaction from its implementation.

2. To questions about the organization and working conditions, respondents gave contradictory answers: 90% noted good management (question 5), but 60% noted insufficient provision of equipment and devices (question 10), and 70% indicated insufficient communication with management (question 6), and low wages (50%). Perhaps these contradictions are objective

in nature: the problem of salaries of young professionals is always and everywhere acute and can be resolved by the efforts of the administration of an educational institution. According to the city works, the average salary of a physical education teacher in the Sverdlovsk region for 2023 is 29,247 rubles; the average salary of a physical education teacher in Yekaterinburg for 2023 is 31,096 rubles. However, most often in vacancies there is a salary of 25,000 rubles (modal) [4]. At the same time, various incentive allowances are not taken into account, which are very limited for young professionals.

3. Regarding management, the main complaint on the part of young specialists is insufficient provision with everything necessary and insufficient communication. If the first one can take into account the financial difficulties of educational institutions, then communication with the administration is entirely in the field of improving the management process. It is not surprising that only half of the respondents would like to continue working in an educational institution, and 60% are not sure about their life prospects in this educational institution.

The question of the clarity of young specialists' understanding of their work expectations is very interesting. 30% of respondents do not understand the requirements imposed on them in their professional activities. Such a high percentage of disoriented teachers is alarming. This question can be interpreted in a broad sense: earlier we noted that the adaptation of a physical education teacher depends on the process of formation of the subjective-personal sphere, ideological norms and values.

And, perhaps, being involved in the process of more informal communication with students, young physical education teachers are experiencing some difficulties with this aspect.

Especially at the moment of extreme socio-political turbulence and the sharp polarization of mass consciousness, especially among young people. These conclusions are of fundamental importance and need further research.

It should be emphasized that the motivation for the activity of a teacher among respondents is very high, in particular, as follows from Table 4, for all respondents, the absolute priority of activity is interesting work, friendly attitude of the management to the team, attention to the opinion of the team from the management and the opportunity to show initiative and entrepreneurship.

Assistance in the adaptation of young specialists was provided mainly by colleagues of young teachers – 80% of respondents reported this; the head of the organization and his deputy – 40% indicated this, friends – 40% of respondents indicated this, and 20% remained without support. It is obvious that in professional adaptation hopes are placed on the teaching staff, senior colleagues and management, and psychological adaptation remains friends. A fairly high percentage of young teachers, for various reasons, were forced to overcome the pain of professional development on their own, which indicates that the management of educational institutions is not attentive enough to this problem.

Nevertheless, 90% of respondents indicated that the team treated them kindly and were ready to provide moral support, which, of course, was a significant help in psychological adaptation. Only 5% of respondents faced obvious unfriendliness. What is very interesting is that 80% of young physical education teachers surveyed noted that colleagues turned to them for practical advice in the field of physical education. It seems that such a situation was very useful

for young professionals in increasing confidence in their professional competence and increased self-esteem, thereby contributing to the adaptation process.

Conclusions. Summing up the results of the study, it can be noted that certain difficulties of the adaptation process of young physical education teachers in Yekaterinburg occur in all types of adaptation and in all its structural components.

A very significant number of young physical education teachers are not confident in their professional knowledge and assess their level very critically.

With a high motivation to become a physical education teacher and motivation for professional development, a significant number of young teachers surveyed are not confident in their professional future in these educational institutions, primarily due to not quite successful communication with the management of educational institutions and insufficient material support for the educational process.

Psychological adaptation in general for the majority proceeded very comfortably thanks to the help and support from the teaching staff. Nevertheless, respondents note a lack of "soft" skills in the field of self-management and gaps in professional training experienced as a state of frustration during the adaptation period.

REFERENCES

1. Nacional'nyj proekt "Obrazovanie". (2019, January 10) [National project "Education"]. Strategiya 24 [Strategy 24]. <https://strategy24.ru/rf/education/projects/natsionalnyy-proekt-obrazovanie>. (In Russian).
2. Vishnevskaja, N. G., & Mukhamatjanova, L. V. (2014). Adaptaciya personala: opredelenie i vidy [Personnel adaptation: definition and types]. *Ekonomika i socium [Economics and Society]*, 2(11), 924–926. (In Russian).
3. Muhamadiyevna A. R., Ulugbekovna N. I. Organization Of Refereeing of Sports Games and Martial Arts //Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies. – 2021. – Т. 2. – С. 251-253.
4. Ахмеджанов М. И., Рахматиллаев М. С. СОРЕВНОВАТЕЛЬНАЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ В СИСТЕМЕ СПОРТИВНОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ ГАНДБОЛИСТОВ //СТУДЕНЧЕСКАЯ НАУКА-ПЕРВЫЙ ШАГ В АКАДЕМИЧЕСКУЮ НАУКУ. - 2022. - С. 549-555.
5. Rakhmatillayev M. METHODS OF SELECTING TALENTED CHILDREN FOR HANDBALL SPORT //Евразийский журнал академических исследований. - 2022. - Т. 2. - №. 11. - С. 935-939.
6. МҶМИНОВ А., РАХМАТИЛЛАЕВ М. TECHNOLOGY OF DEVELOPMENT OF SPEED QUALITIES OF YOUNG HANDBALL PLAYERS //O 'ZBEKISTON MILLIY UNIVERSITETI XABARLARI, 2022,[1/10] ISSN 2181-7324.
7. Ibragimov S. A. et al. Comorbid course of atopic dermatitis with bronchial asthma in children: Frequency, clinical and allergological characteristics //Journal of Critical Reviews. - 2020. - Т. 7. - №. 17. - С. 2317-2321.

8. Kadirov A. METHODS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF PSYCHOPHYSIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF YOUNG FOOTBALL PLAYERS //Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики. - 2022. - Т. 6. - №. 6. - С. 105-119.
9. Кадыров А. МЕТОДИКА РАЗВИТИЯ ПСИХО-ФИЗИОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИК ЮНЫХ ФУТБОЛИСТОВ //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. - 2023. - Т. 2. - №. 3. - С. 1266-1280.
10. Кадыров А., Ибрагимов С. ФИЗИОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ И БИОХИМИЧЕСКИЕ ЗАКОНОМЕРНОСТИ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ТРЕНИРОВОЧНЫХ ЭФФЕКТОВ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ТРЕНИРОВОЧНЫХ ЗАНЯТИЙ //SCHOLAR. - 2023. - Т. 1. - №. 15. - С. 124-140.
11. Rakhimov U. I. ORGANIZING THE TRAINING PROCESS OF 10-12-YEAR-OLD FOOTBALL PLAYERS THROUGH ACTION GAMES //Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal. - 2023. - С. 175-182.
12. Raximov U. I. 10-12 YOSHDAGI YOSH FUTBOLCHILARNI TAYYORGARLIGINING O?ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI //Academic research in educational sciences. - 2022. - Т. 3. - №. 2. - С. 612-616.
13. Abdullayev I. X. IMPROVEMENT OF THE SPECIAL PHYSICAL TRAINING MODEL OF GRECO-ROMAN JUNIOR WRESTLERS //Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal. - 2023. - С. 9-20.
14. Xushnudovich A. I. ANALYZING THE COMPETITIVE PERFORMANCE OF GRECO-ROMAN WRESTLING ATHLETES //E Conference Zone. - 2023. - С. 26-31.
15. Khushnudovich A. I. DEVELOPMENT OF SPECIAL PHYSICAL TRAINING OF GRECO-ROMAN WRESTLERS WITH THE HELP OF SPECIAL SIMULATORS //Conferencea. - 2023. - С. 68-73.
16. Karimova N.Kh. Elmurodova M.U. MANAGEMENT IN THE ACTIVITIES OF SPORTS ORGANIZATIONS //Актуальные проблемы физического воспитания студентов. - 2022. - С. 177-179.
17. Karimova N. Kh, Khasanova I. K, Elmurodova M. U. MENTAL STRESS DURING SPORTS ACTIVITIES //АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ И СПОРТА В СОВРЕМЕННЫХ СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИХ УСЛОВИЯХ. - 2021. - С. 401-403.
18. KARIMOVA N. O 'ZBEKISTONDA SOG 'LOM TURMUSH TARZINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI //Journal of Pedagogical and Psychological Studies. - 2023. - Т. 1. - №. 10. - С. 121-125.
19. Taniqulova Z. R., Karimova N. K. SPORTS SERVICE //Актуальные проблемы физического воспитания студентов. - 2022. - С. 628-630.
20. Karimova N. INNOVATIVE EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES AT THE UNIVERSITY: INNOVATIVE PORTFOLIO TECHNOLOGY //Theoretical & Applied Science. - 2020. - №. 10. - С. 352-356.
21. BEKHZOD K. JISM?NIY TARBIYA DARSLARINI O'QITISHDA ?ARAKATLI O'YINLARNI QO'LLASHNING SAMARADORLIGI //Scienceweb academic papers collection. - 2020.

22. Qo'chqarov S. FUTBOLCHILARDA TEZKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH
23. NING USUL VA USLUBLARI TAXLILI //Scienceweb academic papers collection. - 2020.
24. Казоқов Р. Т., Мирзабдиллаева А. И., Мирзабдиллаева Х. И. МАКТАБГАЧА ТАЪЛИМ МУАССАСАЛАРИДА ТАРБИЯВИЙ ТАДБИРЛАРДА МИЛЛИЙ-МАЪНАВИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШ //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 8. – С. 29-34.
25. Казоқов Р. Т. и др. ПЕДАГОГИКА ОЛИЙ ТАЪЛИМДА КЕЙС-СТАДИ ТАЪЛИМ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСИ АСОСИДА ПЕДАГОГИК МАҲОРАТИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ ЮЗАСИДАН ТАЖРИБА-СИНОВ ИШЛАРИНИНГ НАТИЖАЛАРИ //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 111-115.
26. Kazoqov R. T., Djurabaev A. M. Kredit modul tizimi nima //Ta'limni raqamlashtirish sharoitida pedagog kadrlarni qayta tayyorlash va malakasini oshirish. – 2021. – Т. 4. – №. 4. – С. 198-206.
27. Давурбаева М. Ж., Казоқов Р. Т., Мадаминов М. П. ТАЛАБА ЁШЛАРНИНГ МУСТАҚИЛ ТАЪЛИМ ОЛИШДАГИ БИЛИМ ВА КЎНИКМАЛАРИНИНГ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШДА ИНТЕРНЕТ РЕСУРСЛАРИДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШНИНГ АХАМИЯТИ //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 26-31.
28. Давурбаева М. Ж., Казоқов Р. Т., Мадаминов М. П. ТАЛАБА ЁШЛАРНИНГ МУСТАҚИЛ ТАЪЛИМ ОЛИШДАГИ БИЛИМ ВА КЎНИКМАЛАРИНИНГ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШДА ИНТЕРНЕТ РЕСУРСЛАРИДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШНИНГ АХАМИЯТИ //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 26-31.
29. Давурбаева М.Ж.,Казоқов Р.Т., Мадаминов М.П.Ёшларнинг мустақил таълим олишдаги билим ва кўникмаларининг такомиллаштиришда интернет ресурсларидан фойдаланишнинг ахамияти//ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCE. - 2023/2/14. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 26-31.
30. Казоқов Р. Т., Жўрақўзиев О. О., Эшпўлатов С. С. СПОРТ МУАССАСАЛАРИДА ТАРБИЯВИЙ ТАДБИРЛАРДА МИЛЛИЙ-МАЪНАВИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШ //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 13. – С. 238-248.
31. Казоқов Р.Т., Бўриев Б.Ў., Абдиев Б.Ш., Джўрабаев А.М., Туропов А.Р.КУРАШ МИЛЛИЙ СПОРТ ТУРИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ АСОСИЙ ЙЎНАЛИШЛАРИ // МИЛЛИЙ КУРАШ ТУРЛАРИ ВА УЛАРНИНГ НАЗАРИЙ-АМАЛИЙ МУАММОЛАРИ. - 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 161-163.
32. Джўрабаев А. М., Казоқов Р. Т. Биомеханик таҳлиллар асосида енгил атлетикачиларнинг функционал тайёргарлигидаги корреляция алоқаларининг таҳлили //Yoshlarni qo 'l lab-quvvatlash va aholi salomatligini mustahkamlash yili" ga bag'ishlangan. – 2021. – Т. 4. – №. 4. – С. 198-208.

33. Казоқов Р. Т., Расулов А. Ғ., Бўронов А. Б. СПОРТ МАКТАБЛАРИ ЎҚУВ-МАШҒУЛОТ ГУРУҲЛАРИДА ЁШ ФУТБОЛЧИЛАРНИ ТАНЛОВ УСЛУБИЯТЛАРИНИ АСОСЛАШ //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 15. – С. 38-46.
34. Kazoqov R. T., Bo'ronov A. B. SPORTDAGI DOLZARB YANGILIKLAR //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 15. – С. 47-56.
35. Kazoqov R. T., Pirnazarov S. A., Shamsiddinov S. X. STUDENTS LEARN TO ORGANIZE PROFESSIONAL PHYSICAL TRAINING AND CONTROL PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 1195-1202.
36. Eshpo'latov S. S. METHODS AND PRINCIPLES OF IMPROVING TECHNICAL AND TACTICAL SKILLS AND PHYSICAL TRAINING OF YOUNG VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 1296-1302.
37. Kazoqov R. T., Eshpo'latov S. S. YOUNG VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS ARE THE PROCESSES OF ORGANIZING TRAINING SESSIONS //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 1303-1310.
38. Pirmatov O. Z., Kazakov R. T. ROLE AND PLACE OF SPORTS AND ACTIVE GAMES IN THE GENERAL STRUCTURE OF EDUCATIONAL AND PRODUCTION PRACTICE //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 9. – С. 125-131.
39. Kazakov R. T., Rasulov Q. Q. TRAINING IN INTERNATIONAL WRESTLING TECHNIQUES AND TACTICS //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 9. – С. 180-186.
40. Kazoqov R., Akmuradov M. THE IMPORTANCE OF WORKING MEMORY IN MASTERING JUDO SPORTS TECHNIQUES IN ADOLESCENT ATHLETES //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 10. – С. 489-494.
41. Kazoqov, R., & Akmuradov, M. (2023). PSYCHOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF JUDO. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 481–488.
42. Kazoqov R. T., Umaraliyeva F. T. DRAW A KINESICYCLOGRAM OF SHORT-DISTANCE RUNNING AND BUILD A TIMELINE //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 10. – С. 1201-1208.
43. Kazoqov R. T. et al. IMPROVEMENT OF TECHNICAL TRAINING OF SHORT-DISTANCE ATHLETES //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 10. – С. 1077-1084.
44. Kazoqov R. T. et al. STARTING TECHNIQUE IN SHORT DISTANCE RUNNING //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 10. – С. 1070-1076.
45. Xalmuxamedov R. et al. ANALYSIS OF THE DEPENDENCE OF THE CONDITIONS OF THE MIDDLE MOUNTAIN OF INDICATORS OF THE INTENSITY ZONES OF TRAINING TRAINING LOADS OF QUALIFIED BOXER WOMEN //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 10. – С. 473-483.
46. Turdimuratov Y. A. O 'ZBEKISTONDA BOLALAR SPORTINI RIVOJLANTIRISHGA OID DAVLAT SIYOSATI //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 144-152.

47. Турдимуратов Я. А. КОЧЕВОЕ ХОЗЯЙСТВО УЗБЕКОВ ЮЖНОГО УЗБЕКИСТАНА В КОНЦЕ XIX–НАЧАЛО XX ВВ //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 7. – С. 546-557.
48. Шойимардонов, Ш. А., и др. FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS AND SKILLS IN STUDENTS. вып. 12, Zenodo, декабрь 2023 г.,
49. Умаров Д. Х., Мусаев Б. Б. Сравнительный анализ структуры нагрузки перспективных юных гимнастов в соревновательном макроцикле //Наука и спорт: современные тенденции. – 2015. – Т. 8. – №. 3. – С. 28-31.
50. Kerimov F. et al. Possible associations of 25 (OH) vitamin D status with upper respiratory tract infections morbidity and overtraining syndrome among elite wrestlers //Journal of Physical Education and Sport. – 2019. – Т. 19. – С. 2177-2184.
51. Умаров Д. Х. СПОРТ ТАКОМИЛЛАШУВ БОСҚИЧИДА СПОРТ ГИМАСТИКАЧИЛАРДА ПСИХОЛОГИК КОМПЛЕКС НАЗОРАТНИНГ САМАРАДОРЛИГИНИ АСОСЛАШ //Fan-Sportga. – 2022. – №. 1. – С. 31-33.
52. Умаров Д. Х., Холмуродов Л. З., Қурбонов Х. Х. СПОРТНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ БОСҚИЧИДА ГИМАСТИКАЧИЛАРНИНГ ПСИХОЛОГИК НАЗОРАТ САМАРАДОРЛИГИНИ АСОСЛАШ //Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS). – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 354-362.
53. Umarov D. X. et al. JISMONIY MASHQLAR YORDAMIDA MAKTABGASCHA YOSH DAGI BOLALARNING JISMONIY SIFATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH //Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS). – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 363-372.
54. Умаров Д. Х., Умаров М. Н., Эштаев А. К. Оздоровительно-развивающие виды основной гимнастики: Учебное пособие //Издательскополграфический отдел УзГос ИФК. – 2006.
55. Bobomurodov A. E. The specific features of agility in preschool children //Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal. – 2021. – Т. 2021. – №. 06. – С. 101-111.
56. Muxitdinovich, F. Y. "Synergetic effect-As an Innovative approach to the Development of the Way of Thinking of Physical Culture and Sports Specialists." *European Journal of Research and Reflections in Education Sciences* 8.12 (2020): 165-170.
57. Якубов, Фазлиддин Мухитдинович. "Бўлажак жисмоний тарбия ва спорт мутахассисларида спорт тафаккури ва унинг услубларини яратиш орқали тафаккур тарзини такомиллаштириш йўллари." *Фан-Спортга* 4 (2019): 17-22.
58. Muqimov, Olim. "СПОРТНИНГ ЖАМИЯТДА ТУТГАН УРНИ ВА ИЖТИМОЙ-ТАРБИЯВИЙ АҲАМИЯТИ." *Физическое воспитание, спорт и здоровье* 1 (2020).